

Synthesis of exploratory research

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POZNAN

January 2018

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7501703>

*Akceptuję dokument
od str. 1 do 42*

**PEŁNOMOCNIK PREZYDENTA
DS. FUNDUSZY EUROPEJSKICH**

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DOCUMENT PROPERTIES

Nature Document	Synthesis of exploratory research in Poznan
Work Package	WP3 task 3.1
Task Leader	UEL
Authors	OSMOS (Eric Haas and Stephan Kampelmann) AMU (Lidia Poniży and Iwona Zwierzchowska)
Dissemination level	Private – WP 1,2, 3 leads and co-ordinator
Version	20180227_Summary of exploratory research WP3
Status of Document	Draft
Deadline	28 February 2018

Table 1. Synthesis of exploratory research in Poznan

WP	3
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Fieldwork period	The survey was sent out in August 2017. The interviews were carried out on 20-21 November 2017. The workshop was held on 16 January 2018.
Interviewers	Eric Haas and Stephan Kampelmann (Osmos), Lidia Poniży and Iwona Zwierzchowska and (AMU), supported by Stuart Connop (UEL), Agnieszka Dziubała, Agnieszka Osipiuk and Marta Czaplińska (City of Poznan) and translator Katarzyna Matschi
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Output	Audio recordings of interviews Annotated city maps Completed stakeholder maps Interviewer notes Signed consent forms Photos from meetings and site visits Synthesis (this document)

Table of contents

Objectives of the exploratory research	5
Setting and context.....	5
Methodology	6
Executive summary.....	8
Map with projects/sites.....	9
Theme-specific summaries	10
1. About the city	10
2. State of NbS (and related projects).....	15
3. Relevant documents.....	23
4. Finance	24
5. Business	24
6. Community	25
7. Knowledge-infrastructure-environment.....	26
8. Governance and decision making.....	28
9. Stakeholders.....	29
10. Driving themes for NbS in Poznan.....	30
Nature-based Solutions and Connecting Nature in Poznan: where do we stand?.....	31
Appendix 1: Annotated city maps.....	38
Appendix 2: Examples of stakeholder map.....	39
Appendix 3. Questionnaire used for interviews.....	40

Objectives of the exploratory research

1. Explore NbS-type projects:
 - a. identifying NbS that are planned or implemented in Poznań;
 - b. learning about what made good projects a success and what led bad projects to be unsuccessful.
2. Connect with the local actors face-to-face and allow them to have the chance to express themselves. Gain an overview of organisational conditions, including collecting information about knowledge of NbS among civil servants from Poznań City Hall and related units and organisations.
3. Identify other relevant actors (both individuals and organisations) and their capacity/interest in contributing to Connecting (for WP 1, 2 and 4).
4. Help define contacts and engagement strategies for stakeholders relevant to WP1-3 to ensure positive and constructive engagement with the project.
5. Explore organizational and financial mechanisms of NbS creation in Poznań.
Explore NbS potential in solving urban problems of Poznań and define the general narrative driving NbS in this city.

Setting and context

This document is based on two main sources: firstly, exploratory research based on a survey carried out by AMU during the second half of 2017. Carried out in collaboration with the City of Poznań, the survey focused on NbS in Poznań City Hall and related budgetary units, companies in which the City of Poznan has a share, and associations of which City of Poznan is a member. Secondly, exploratory interviews carried out by Osmos on November 20-21 2017. The latter interviews were organised by the Connecting Nature team from the City of Poznan.

These activities are part of Task 3.1: Capturing and sharing pre-existing front-runner city expertise in delivering scaled-up nature-based solutions approach comprising multifunctional objectives (Start: M1 End: M12. Lead Partner: UEL. Partners involved: All front-runner cities, AMU). According to the Connecting Nature description of work, Task 3.1 will involve “exploiting the existing expertise developed by the learning-by-doing approach adopted by each front-runner city (partners 2,3 and 4). Partner 18 (AMU) will work with the City of Poznan to capture the city’s current exemplars. Partner 15 (UEL) will work with Glasgow and Genk to capture theirs. Support in GIS spatial analysis and capacity mapping will both be provided by partner 27 (GeoGraphic). This pre-existing capacity will be used for the development by UEL (partner 15) in partnership with front-runner city Partners (2,3 and 4) of a dissemination document to outline the specific nature-based solution exemplar delivery programmes and scale-up opportunities exploited in each front-runner city. In so doing, it will begin the iterative capture and transfer of adaptive governance processes to work packages 1 and 2 and, ultimately, fast-follower and multiplier cities. Outputs from this Task will feed into the knowledge mapped and systematised in Tasks 1.1 to 1.3, led by UDC (partner 16), and the co-development processes in Tasks 2.1 to 2.4, led by Drift (partner 14).”

The milestone that is associated with this task (Milestone 3.1) is a draft of the KPIs for the FRCs to be assessed using the Eklipse framework (due in M12); the deliverable (Deliverable 3.1) is a report on FRCs current expertise and experience in nature-based solutions based on a synthesis of experiential workshops and concluding with a process chart for transferrable KPIs approach to NbS (due in M16).

The interviews were organised by the CN team of the City of Poznan based on exchanges with Osmos (Eric Haas, Adrian Vickery Hill and Stephan Kampelmann). A site tour was organised by the city of Poznan, visiting a range of urban renovation projects and emblematic green spaces in Poznan.

Methodology

Interviews

The team from the City of Poznan invited both internal (i.e. from the city council) and external (from other public organisations or NGOs) colleagues covering themes related to public space, environment, water management, mobility, planning and sustainability.

Regarding the interviews carried out in November 2017, each conversation lasted approximately one hour and was conducted by Eric and Stephan with support from Stuart (UEL) and Kasia (translator). Notes and audio recordings were produced during the interviews. The interview was loosely structured by a questionnaire including ten themes and a range of sub-questions for each theme (see Appendix). The themes were drawn from a review by UEL of the Eklipse framework and related documents, plus specific financial and economic development questions from TCD. The same themes are used below to structure the synthesis of the discussions. Interviewers were encouraged to make use of additional supporting materials: a stakeholder map and a city map. Examples of how these documents were used are provided below.

Survey of NbS in Poznań City Hall and related organisations

A questionnaire on existing NbS experiences was prepared by AMU and consulted by the Project Coordination and Urban Regeneration Office (City of Poznań). The questionnaire was supplemented with introductory information about the CONNECTING Nature project. To facilitate good understanding of questions, a definition of NbS together with an open list of NbS examples were provided. Respondents were asked to fill in internet-based or standard paper forms. The questionnaire included questions concerning facts and respondents' opinions. It consisted of general as well as detailed questions concerning NbS exemplars.

The questionnaire was distributed by email to 20 different departments of Poznań City Hall and related organisations, companies and associations in August 2017. 'Representatives from the following organisations replied to the questionnaire:

1. Office of the Mayor of the City (Gabinet Prezydenta)
2. Aquanet S.A.
3. Road Management Board in Poznan (Zarząd Dróg Miejskich w Poznaniu)
4. Department of Transport and Greenery (Wydział Transportu i Zieleni)
5. Palm House (Palmiarnia Poznańska)
6. Zoological Garden (Ogród Zoologiczny)
7. Metropolis of Poznań Association (Stowarzyszenie Metropolia Poznań)
8. Poznań Town Planning Office (Miejska Pracownia Urbanistyczna)
9. Municipal Transport Company in Poznań (Miejskie Przedsiębiorstwo Komunikacyjne w Poznaniu)
10. Department of Environmental Protection (Wydział Ochrony Środowiska)
11. Department of Economic Activity and Agriculture (Wydział Działalności Gospodarczej i Rolnictwa)
12. Department of Urbanism and Architecture (Wydział Urbanistyki i Architektury)
13. Department of Real Estate Management (Wydział Gospodarki Nieruchomościami)
14. Municipal Greenery Management Board in Poznan (Zarząd Zieleni Miejskiej)
15. The Board of Municipal Residential Resources (Zarząd Komunalnych Zasobów Lokalowych sp. z o. o.)
16. The Project Coordination and Urban Regeneration Office (Biuro Koordynacji Projektów i Rewitalizacji Miasta) (4 questionnaires)

Data collected was analyzed using standard descriptive statistics and is summarised in green boxes throughout this document.

Executive summary

Our exploratory research confirmed Poznan's status as a European frontrunner for Nature-based Solutions (NbS). This conclusion is not only based on an inventory of many small-scale environmental projects, which often involving a participatory element, which the city authorities initiated or accompanied over the last 5 years; it also accounts for the fact that Poznan features a rare example of a visionary, ambitious and large-scale NbS that has been maintained over decades. It is a solution that improves the quality of life of many Poznanians every single day by providing cleaner air to breathe and access to vast recreational green spaces in the vicinity of their homes, while also creating habitats for many species of plants and animals. We refer of course to the city's elaborate system of green rings and wedges whose inception goes back to the work of urbanist Hermann Joseph Stübben, but which owes its current form to the ideas that the architect Wladyslaw Czarnecki together with the naturalist Adam Wodziczko developed in the 1930s.

Many of the conversations we led in November 2017 that are summarized below evolved in some way or another around this historic "Nature-based Solution" in Poznan. Many interviewees expressed concern that the system of green wedges and rings is coming under untenable pressure from Poznan's booming housing market, with new developments eating into preserved green spaces. Others argued that the system still offers room for improvement, for instance in the dense city center where the wedges become narrower and high-quality green space is scarce. One interviewee also referred to the "innovative" approaches to rainwater management that were implemented in Poznan during the first half of the 20th century and that could serve as inspiration for finding (nature-based) solutions to the city's current flood risk. Almost a hundred years after its inception, the system also offers opportunities that could not have been foreseen, such as the use of the green corridors for improving the bicycle mobility around the metropolitan area.

Against the backdrop of this impressive historical achievement, a series of recent projects and initiatives complement the picture of Poznan current standpoint in terms of NbS. First, there are several large-scale projects with potential relevance for the objectives of Connecting Nature: an ambitious city-wide rainwater strategy is currently being developed; the **Warta Riverside development in the Wilda district**, including an urban beach and the bicycle path "Wartostrada"; several city parks will be renovated or created; and sizable post-industrial areas redeveloped over the course of the next years. Second, we identified a surge of initiatives at the local level: these concern the creation of pocket parks (such as the **Jezyce Pocket Park**), green roofs, **social gardens** and other small-scale initiatives whose combined impact could be just as large as the city-wide flagship projects.

Like in other European cities, it seems that the City Hall and its related departments and organizations are very much central to the development of NbS in Poznan. Other stakeholders, such as civil society organisations and businesses, seem to have played a less visible role so far. This being said, the relatively recent creation of civic budgets and the timid but increasing proliferation of collective gardening and other activist-based environmental initiatives are indicators that the development of NbS could become more of a co-creational process between different types of stakeholders. A key challenge in this regard seems to be finding ways to align NbS with business interests. Indeed, Poznan's business community has yet to identify opportunities in this area. More worrisome it that powerful economic players – such as real estate developers – are considered by many interviewees as opponents rather than partners. This is all the more problematic as Poznan's success as one of Poland's fastest developing and most prosperous cities, is chiefly an economic one. This success fuels some of the above mentioned NbS projects: a prosperous local economy also means a prosperous municipality that can invest in green infrastructure, or successfully attract European funding and subsidies for such investments. Conversely, the successful implementation of NbS could also affect positively real estate values, thereby creating the scope of win-win situations between real estate developers and advocates of NbS interventions. This being said, Poznan's historic achievement of maintaining a fully-fledged nature-based solution – the system of green wedges and rings – over such a long timespan could become a victim of the city's economic expansion.

Map with projects/sites

Figure 1. Map of Poznan with project sites.

Source and link: <http://bit.ly/2muuoUm>

Theme-specific summaries

1. About the city

1.1. Perceived current major challenges / issues

- The morphology of Poznan is still marked by **a system of green rings and green wedges** proposed by the urbanist Wladyslaw Czarnecki in the 1930s. Roughly speaking the system of green wedges follows the existing natural geographical structure of the city where smaller rivers (the Bogdanka, Cybina and Główna as well as the Głuszykna and Michałówka) meet up with the Warta River streaming from south to north. Today, the majority of the green wedges are covered with forests which under current zoning plans cannot be used for construction. Inside the city boundaries, there are also around 8,500 hectares of agricultural land that can potentially be used for development - especially land that was left fallow after the collapse of collective agriculture in the early 1990s. Almost all interviewees spontaneously referred to the Czarnecki system and commented positively on its value and function for the city of Poznan. There also seems to be a strong awareness among the general population about the value of this system. The interviewee from the Greenery Department of the Road Management Board explicitly mentioned the goal of maintaining and developing this system of green rings and wedges.
- The system has come **under a lot of pressure during recent years**. As one interviewee put it: "Since the mid-1990s a race to development started". The problem seems to be one of striking a balance between maintaining the green wedges system while also catering to the pressure from the real estate market that pushes towards housing development. New housing also comes with other pressures, such as the need for additional parking space, increased rainwater run-off, etc. There have been local petitions against changing zoning rules in favour of new construction and for preserving green zones; halting urban sprawl is also one of the priorities of City Hall. Several interviewees said that Poznan should reinforce its plans and strategies so that the city can develop and provide new housing without disrupting the historic system of green spaces.
- The interviewees reported that the city suffers from urban sprawl, creating quite substantial problems caused by increased commuter traffic. Like in other cities the **main drivers for urban sprawl** are noise and pollution in the city center, but chiefly the considerable gap in real estate values between the city center and suburban areas. According to the director of the city's revitalization department, some people who previously moved to the suburbs are affluent enough and ready to come back to the city center. There are also a number of vacant plots close to the city center that could be developed for housing.
- More generally, **mobility is a central challenge for many Poznanians**. Road congestion is high and there is a strong pressure to increase the number of parking spaces, mostly due to the large number of commuters. It is difficult to commute into the city center from the North; residents of that area would like to see a new tram connection. One interviewee pointed out that there has been a lot of efforts to improve mobility within the city center, especially around Święty Marcin Avenue. However, the park & ride system could be improved. A clear challenge for the city seems to be finding ways to reconcile car mobility (parking, congestion, roads, pollution) and greenery.
- **The city of Poznan is relatively compact**; this is perceived as positive but makes it also difficult to identify and develop new green areas. According to some interviewees, there are grounds that could be put to better use in the city center, which is perceived as not being green

enough. Some mentioned a desire to extend the “biologically active areas”, an objective that still needs to be defined and operationalised. Better use of open space has the potential for achieving this aim.

- The freshwater and sewage systems are currently being renovated and in the phase of completion. The water quality in the river has improved over time, but the **problem of rainwater management** has yet to be resolved. Especially if one takes into account further urban development (buildings, parkings, etc) and the challenges caused by climate change. Rainwater currently flows into a combined sewage system. In total, around 12 water channels feed into the Warta River that runs through Poznan (these streams are managed by the province of Wielkopolska, a situation that creates a governance challenge at the city level). The issue of rainwater management has been underestimated in the past. The areas of Wilda and Jezyce experienced water absorption problems (also for trees, who stand in water because it cannot infiltrate). During episodes of strong storms, like those that occurred in the summer of 2010, Poznan can become flooded. The cost of increasing the capacity of a pumping station after the events in 2010 were reported at 40 million PLN. It is unclear whether the pumping stations will be able to cope in 5 or 10 years, which means that the current configuration does not represent a permanent and sustainable solution. Aquanet –the city’s official body responsible for the water and sewage infrastructure - estimates that there are 40 locations in permanent risk of (pluvial) flooding. The problem is not the Warta River itself, but rather the rest of the system. There were natural water courses and very old water retention systems; but, following the massive development of housing and the associated impermeabilization of agricultural land and disappearance and canalisation of natural watercourses , this system partly lost its efficiency.
- It should be noted that water-related challenges and problems are quite location specific, with rainwater management being acute in the west of the city, whereas issues with groundwater/snow water melt appear in the southeast. It is likely that this requires adaptive solutions based on the needs of specific location (as opposed to one-size-fits-all).
- According to some interviewees, the city is marked by **high temperature swings** (although, in fact, Poznań’s UHI (Urban Heat Island) is moderate in comparison with other cities of similar size). In the city center, heat island effects are reported during the summer; there were several winters without snow, but the regular dispersion of salt on streets when temperatures drop below zero exerts pressure on local vegetation, and especially trees, due to highly saline run-off of salt from gritting in winter. This phenomenon appears to exacerbate problems with soil degradation in the centre. As a consequence, many street trees are reported to have been unable to collect enough water during the winter. The interviews revealed a perception that this problem seems to be more salient in Poznan than other Polish cities. The large fluctuations in water and temperature levels render the management of the river’s embankment both important and difficult. In the 1970s, a concrete embankment was built along the Warta river in some areas of the city center. Currently, a large-scale project developed by the Water Management Board tries to renaturalise the embankment, aiming at natural retention and infiltration of water in a larger area. The embankments are being more and more used by Poznanians and tourists; people spend more time there. The renaturalisation of the concrete embankments foresees recreation facilities, but only in areas where the embankment can be made accessible through stairways.
- It should be noted that **greenspace is not evenly distributed throughout the entire area of Poznan**: there is more greenspace in peri-urban areas compared to the old city centre. This is possibly a result of the green wedge system (i.e. wedges get narrower the closer one moves to the centre). The relative lack of green space in the city centre seems to drive the perceived need to insert green pockets back into the dense centre where many of the above challenges/issues are exacerbated by the lack of greenspace. Moreover, biodiversity

considerations appear to have received a relatively low priority in current greenspace strategies.

1.2. Perceived opportunities

- Aquanet/City Hall want to go in the **direction of a nature-based solution to flood risk**, to use nature in an intelligent and innovative solution. They will establish a spatial planning solution that will allow the natural infrastructure to cope with predicted rises in volume and intensity of rainfall events. This will turn rainwater into an opportunity. Three categories of retention have been identified: attenuated flows, retention on the spot and a combination with greenery. The goal is to generate projects that will show that it is possible to combine green and blue infrastructure solutions. Moreover, Aquanet/City Hall are currently working on a water management strategy with Arup Polska. The latter are mapping resources, for instance what kind of management tools and instruments could be enabled. Both specialists from the municipality and from Aquanet are involved in this work. In the framework of this study, a mathematical simulation of very high rainfalls will be developed.
- The Road Department is exploring the possibility of **using microspaces or small patches of land for greening the city center**. This being said, they think that parks and gardens would be a better location for big NbS projects, but this would be the realm of other departments. For several years, the Road Board has been cooperating with the Housing Estate Associations and private individuals to create “pocket parks”.
- In the 1960s the Warta river was still extensively used for water transport; but nowadays freight traffic on the river has nearly dropped to zero. However, some shift is apparent as a new strategy for inland waterway navigation is prepared at a national level in order to prepare the rivers for inland freight transport. **This forces Poznan to think more about the use of the river and water**, which will be turned into part of the network of international waterways.
- There are recent initiatives of **cooperation at the scale of the metropolitan area** (which includes a number of municipalities around Poznan). This is a promising development, especially with regards to mobility policies. Respondents of the survey also pointed to NbS that could be applied on a broader, supralocal scale, such as building a network of regional connections.
- There has been intensive **international cooperation** between City of Poznan, the Greater Poland Voivodenship (Wielkopolska Province) and the province of Drenthe (and the City of Assen). Agnieszka Osipiuk, a member of the CN team from the City of Poznan, worked for this partnership. What is more, a consortium including several Dutch consultancy companies produced a Development Strategy for River Water in Poznan in 2012. These water-related cooperations between Poznan and The Netherlands are an asset that could perhaps be reactivated for NbS in CN. There has also been cooperation with the Senate of Berlin regarding the methodology and design of public spaces; Berlin is also cited as a reference for community garden projects both by representatives of the grassroots movements and the City Hall.
- There are some **post-industrial areas with big potential for redevelopment** into multifunctional areas (commercial, housing, green spaces). Examples include the slaughterhouse (privately owned), the old gas plant (the city has a minor share; different public state gas companies, apparently also Aquanet holds a share) and a 200 acre area besides the Poznan central station (previously used for train maintenance). The former gas plant is still used by some companies, but these are expected to leave within the next 5 years: a

negotiation about the future of the site will sooner or later start. The slaughterhouse will be sold and redeveloped with a mixed program (housing + commercial) to a consortium of parties. The city expects this to happen over the course of the next year. Currently the city already has supported some young entrepreneurs to use the site temporarily, thereby taking the lead in place-making. As for the railway redevelopment plot, the timeline so far is not known, but the areas are recognised for their development potential as well. The revitalization of the post-industrial areas will require new mobility infrastructures (new roads, new pedestrian bridge) and additional parking spaces.

- The city of Poznan has established an instrument to **facilitate bottom-up initiatives**, in accordance with the city's policies. This system consists of **civic budgets** (to a maximum of around 30k EUR (120k PLN) to be allocated to specific projects after a public voting process (the population votes for projects of their interest and preference) after they first pass an internal "due diligence" test that serves to check whether the proposed project are in-line with local policies and regulations. Some projects included activities like urban gardening, new public greenspace, etc. The selection process has evolved to react to a bias towards larger projects that was apparent in the early stages. There are now two scales of funding: larger (city scale) and smaller (local scale) projects.
- **Roof space and wall spaces** were identified as opportunities for greening that are not currently being exploited to a great extent. There is an awareness about this opportunity but, so far, no strategy/policy has been developed. Green roofs can be included in the spatial planning process. In general, according to Polish national law, green roofs can be considered in spatial planning as biologically active surfaces. In practice, however, this can be difficult since sometimes green roof surfaces can be used to replace ground-based green spaces, which have a different biological quality. Overall, green roofs and/or walls need to be better integrated into spatial planning, for instance into the master plans approved by the spatial development committee.
- Another area of potential opportunity are the **Warta embankments in the city center of Poznan**. One section is already planned for renaturalisation (see below), but there may be further opportunities for introducing innovative NbS in additional sections.
- **Protection and preservation of biodiversity and creation of a network of protected areas.** Natural areas protected by law in Poznan do not form a connected network, therefore it is necessary to increase the cohesion of the protected areas system as well as to ensure the continuity and spatial cohesion of ecological corridors. Biological invasive alien species pose a threat to biodiversity conservation, in addition to the loss of habitats. They are a problem, especially in protected areas, where they displace native plant species for the protection of which these areas have been created. In order to protect and sustainably use biodiversity, and thus maintain the appropriate status of species and natural habitats, it is necessary to strive to maintain the continuity of the natural systems of the city with the regional, European system, undertaking rational actions. The achievement of the objective will enable the creation and development of a network of valuable nature areas and the designation of new protected areas, management and restoration of habitats of the most endangered species.

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2. State of NbS (and related projects)

2.1 Past projects that could be used as NbS exemplars

Data collected in the exploratory survey among City Hall departments and related organizations indicates that 90% of respondents had previously heard about Nature-based Solutions and green infrastructure. More than half of them (63%) reported that the activities of the department in which they work contribute to the emergence of NbS. A summary of the actions identified by respondents that are undertaken in their respective units is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Actions in the field of NbS undertaken by the City Hall and related units.

The representatives of surveyed entities mentioned a number of projects related to NbS, some of which are planned, some are in the implementation phase and some of them have already been implemented (respectively 39%, 33%, 28%).

- The **historical green wegde system in the city of Poznan** could be considered as an NbS exemplar. It designates corridors that are ecological links between the areas of the wedge-shaped greenery system of the city. A current project aims at identifying corridors to ensure the continuity of greenery as well as to indicate attractive areas for pedestrians and bicycle mobility through the corridors. Related to this are different initiatives aimed at **improving the soft mobility infrastructure of Poznan**, for instance, **new cycling connections between Poznań and the Swarzędz commune**. Using the location in the green wedge in the east of the city, the planned infrastructure should encourage residents of both cities to choose a bicycle as an alternative means of transport. The **project “Wartostrada”** consists of the construction of a pedestrian and cycle system along both banks the Warta river valley on the floodplain and embankment. Wartostrada as a bicycle route has the function of an alternative system of commuting that supplement the public transport system.
- There are no recent experiences with nature-based water management projects, except a few small-scale water gardens. But Aquanet has been able to identify and characterize the historic approach to rainwater management; **in the Solacz area** to manage groundwater, three beautiful ponds were built, a recreational lake and a bypass. Developed in 1910, then in the 1930s there were nice villas developed in the same area. This became one of the most desirable areas to live in Poznan. The **Malta lake and the ponds close to Antonin**, which clean the water of the Cybina River that flows into the Malta Lake, were cited as examples of recreational areas created in the late 1940s early 1950s.

- **“A 100 trees for Lazarz”**: a bottom-up project started in autumn 2016 and financed through the civic budget (ca 110.000 zlotys, including one year of maintenance). The project is being carried out in cooperation with the Road Board.
- **“Pocket Park Jezyce”**: created in 2015 on public ground. There were new building conditions placed on the housing developer by the Road Department with regards to a certain greenery area between the street and the building. Inhabitants participated, were consulted on the project: they wanted something else, a more social aspect of the space, an organized, formalized park. The park included high diversity, different types of plants. Different types of surfaces, less pavement. Furniture, table, natural formed greenery. The housing developer did not erect the final version; the project that came out of the citizen participation was more expensive and was not fully financed by the developer. The city supported this project, and the real estate developer donated the money that was budgeted for the green area to the Road Board to co-fund the development of the space. The space is managed by the Road Board.
- **Greenery established along the Stabilewskiego Avenue**. This was an important project. After illegal parking on strips of greenspace, strong pressure was applied by the hospital for extra parking places. They introduced a compromise, using a surface that could absorb rainwater. They use crushed stones (gravel) on the sidewalks and coarser gravel in the parking. They combined this with retaining the greenspace.
- **Revitalisation of Warta embankment in the city center of Poznan**. The restructuring of 4 kilometers of embankments in the city of Poznan has been designed. The plan is to use stone baskets (gabions) that are to be covered by soil and grass. There are several functions to the system, including avoiding erosion and flooding. The system would also enable water infiltration and retention. This project is in the status of the last administrative decisions. The Water Management Board has developed the construction design and is now seeking ways to finance the operation. A part of the project is likely to be financed, notably a pilot section between two bridges 2 kilometers apart in the city center (20 million zlotys for this part). The project could potentially result in more maintenance of the grass layer in the beginning; but after several years, they need to be maintained only twice a year. Reference projects are: Wroclaw (Odra) and projects along the Prosna river. Estimate for flow in the Warta in the case of extreme water events: 800 m³/s. Normal flow: 40 m³/s.
- **Municipal beaches**. Around 2010, there was a general atmosphere in city for a need to reconnect with the river. Popular slogans that appeared in the media were “Poznan forgot about the river” or “The city turned its back on the river”. This was partly meant as an accusation against the city administration. There was a perceived need by Poznanians for recreation in a green environment, close to the city. This led to a regeneration process of the river banks that is still on-going. The municipality reacted by developing different interventions along the banks of the Warta river (CN colleague Marta was closely involved in this process): It started with the temporary use of art (see KontenerArt) in that area. Since 2012, from June until August the municipal beaches operate in Chwaliszewo. Every year the city council improved the management of the beaches; there has been an evaluation and adjustment of the procedures. There is an annual public tender for receiving a subsidy; parts of the activities proposed by the winning bid should be free and the consumption of alcohol is regulated. The annual events on the banks of the Warta River are mostly related to recreation and sport during the summer and target various age groups. In 2018, there will be one big location with a public beach show-casing NbS. The idea is to create a location in which “a part of the countryside is brought into the city”.

- **Workers allotment gardens.** Most of them are situated along the Warta in the south, which are the cheapest green areas in the city and some of them situated on areas at flood risk. There are 92 allotment gardens, with ca 100-1000 plots in each of them. In total, they account for almost 19,000 individual plots, which means that a relatively large number of Poznanians has access to this type of green infrastructure. The law on allotment gardens was changed in 2013 and regulates how the Polish Association of Allotment Gardens operates. While they should be in principle open to the public, some gardens are relatively closed; there might be scope for opening them up more to non-gardeners to improving the way the gardens are managed.

- Partly based on examples of **collective urban gardening** in other European cities (especially Berlin), at least three initiatives of “**social gardens**” have appeared in Poznan in recent years. One of them is carried out by the “**Kolektyw Kąpielisko**”, a non-profit organisation founded by a group of landscape architects, architects, designers and gardeners. Kolektyw Kąpielisko (Bathing Pool Collective) was formed in the framework of the “Generator Malta”. The group was interested in social gardening as a means of urban revitalisation. This collective runs a social garden situated next to an old outdoor swimming pool (hence the name) in the Kasprowicza Park. The city administration wants to identify more spaces for **social and collective gardening**. One strategy is to open existing gardens schools and preschool/kindergarten to the public. This is happening in the context of a **pilot project in Kindergarten Nr. 42** run by Magdalena Garczarczyk (one of the interviewees). This project will involve the establishment of an open garden in the Wilda district, an area that is struggling with low access to greenery. As part of the project, an existing garden will be modernized based on the concept of a "natural playground", and part of area will be accessible to residents as a place of rest for parents and a place to play for children. There will also be a social garden that residents and pre-school children will be able to use. Initially, the garden will be open during the kindergarten’s working hours, but with time it will also be open on weekends and holidays and will be available to the general public. The garden is planned to hold educational workshops related to gardening, as well as special events such as birthdays, picnics, and festivities. The interviewees insisted that the function of social gardens is to activate the neighborhoods; they have an influence on the city’s development. Most of them are more about making social connections than the production of food. One challenge associated with developing social gardens is the strong presence of more traditional allotment garden sites that are widespread in Poznan (see above). Typically, people interested in managing social gardens are already managing their own allotments and, as a consequence, are less inclined to engage in new projects. On the other hand, new residents that move to Poznan from elsewhere might be interested in joining community gardens. In kindergartens, gardens are being modernized in such a way as to make use of natural solutions, in contrast to ready-made structures installed on playgrounds. For example, the gardens are equipped with earth mounds, tunnels, labyrinths with bushes, wicker shacks, sensory paths with the use of natural materials, meadows as a place of nature observation, houses for insects and birds, barrels for rainwater, composters, etc. In addition, training and promotional activities are carried out in the field of creating natural playgrounds, e.g. workshops for pre-school staff and a catalogue of good practices in the area of pre-school garden arrangements.

- **Park in Chwaliszewo:** The water course of the Warta River had been changed in the 1960s/1970s. The northern part of the area was used for circus and fairs and as a temporary car park; a buffer car park. It was realized that this area had deteriorated. The project involved the construction of the park "Old Warta River Bed" in the area of Czartoria - Chwaliszewo – Mostowa streets. The park is a big success: winning second best project in a national competition for public space. They organized workshops bringing together experts and citizens; they developed together the guidelines of what is needed, what should be done. Local residents and people from the area were taken into account: the residential community was

consulted and influenced, for example, the design of the Wartofrajda equipment for which parents and children expressed their needs with respect to the playground in this area

- The finalised design was informal, completed by architects of the 1050 Architecture Studio. The River Bed Park takes inspiration from the old river bed, and there is an element of water management in the park; gravel patches alongside paths for water absorption. The gravel patches were retrofitted this year, after observation of the opportunity for water retention. The **KontenerART** (“mobile culture center”) started in the Jezyce district in 2010. Since 2012 it has been situated at the edge of the in Park in Chwaliszewo. One of the interviewees stressed that residents are not completely happy about the KontenerART (level of noise, high traffic). The residents assumed there would be two or three events during the summer; they welcomed the idea of small events. The reality has been a much more intensive programming. Instead of the KontenerART project, residents appear to favour a playground to be situated on that spot. The Wartofrajda playground has been recently established in the Summer 2017. The principle of renovation of parks is to get back to historical values, but without necessarily going back to the initial design. In the 1950s and 1960s, there was less variety in species. Today more varieties are introduced in the parks. One interviewee pointed out a change in mentalities and expectations regarding green spaces: “People used to look at plants, now they want to use the green spaces: playgrounds, workout, recreational places. Now people are expecting more and more facilities in parks, we have to reintroduce green again.”
- **Consolidation of the park area in the Rataje district.** This area was initially planned in the 1970s and is now in secondary planning stage. The Rataje Park covers almost 15 ha of undeveloped land in the vicinity of housing estates built in the 70s and 80s of the 20th century consisting of 5 and 10 storey buildings. So far there seems to be no clear overriding concept for the entire space. There were no participatory workshops in the beginning of this project. Partly related to the complicated legal status, different plots. There was no focus on rainwater. The surface of the park should be as diverse of possible. The municipality introduced species that are better able to retain water. The municipality employed a “water management inspector”: due to this, water consumption could be reduced by 30% and information about water absorption and irrigation was gathered. The municipality wants to integrate the entire irrigation activities. Irrigation systems exist in 13 parks, and the water management inspector was in charge of all of them. There has not been any coordination yet between Aquanet (Dudlik) and the water inspector.
- For the last two or three years there has been a **compost plant run by a PPP in Morasko**; the subcontractors bring the organic material to this plant. The organic waste of households appears to go to this plant. The compost is not systematically used in the city’s parks. In November 2017, the city council prepared a law for segregate waste bin.
- In 2012, the city cooperated with international partners for the “**Development Strategy River Water Poznan**”. The study is summarised by the Rotterdam Center for Resilient Delta Cities as follows: “In recent years the Polish City of Poznan has experienced heavy floods from the River Warta which revealed the necessity for interventions to improve the river safety. Also in the last decades the City of Poznan has turned its back to the river resulting in the river zone being an unattractive area in the center of this appealing city. The Development Strategy combines water safety measures with interventions to increase the attractiveness and socio-economic strength of the city. The financial and economic feasibility of the proposed interventions have been integrated in the strategy.”
 - o <https://www.royalhaskoningdhv.com/en-gb/projects/development-strategy-river-water-in-poznan-poland/6025>
 - o <http://rdcroterdam.com/projects/development-strategy-for-river-warta-in-poznan/>

- Another interesting project is the **creation of a honey garden** in the Old Zoo. The aim of the project is to create a living environment for pollinating insects and to increase their populations in the agglomeration of the City of Poznan. It would consist in designating plots and sowing annual pollen and nectar-rich plants every year. The plots would be sown by children from Jezyce schools, thus participating actively in the project. Suitable perennial plantings have been used to attract butterflies to the park. Moreover, In the Old Zoo it is also planned to build a rainwater collection system from the aviary building and then directing it to the ponds located within the Zoo. The ponds now are supplied with water from the municipal sewage system - a planned system of bringing rainwater to the ponds would enable Zoo to reduce costs of water. Another element is the completion of works related to the improvement of aesthetic values of the Old Zoo by planting boxwoods and roses in the park area and by removing unnecessary bushes.
- **Also in the Old Zoo a revitalization of herbal garden is planned.** The present herbal garden will be divided thematically into protected Polish plants and herbs (spicy, medicinal and used in cosmetics). The current herbal garden is located in the area of the Old Zoo between Bukowska Street and Zwierzyniecka Street, Gajowa and Kraszewskiego Street.
- **Installation of nesting boxes for birds** reducing insect pests - flies, black flies, mosquitoes, using natural control methods by enhancing swift populations. Swifts are birds that do not build standalone nests in vegetation. Instead they settle in any large enough and safe crevice. Formerly inhabiting rock crevices, swifts adapted to the conditions prevailing in cities, when high stone buildings with numerous holes and crevices appeared. They have been able to utilise both old construction and new-build made from concrete slabs. When the insulation of buildings began, their number decreased.
- **Planting of ivy at the "Lech" tram stop** at the level of the entry to the tram tunnel of the "Franowo" route. On the retaining walls of the entrance to the tunnel, spray painted graffiti appears. To improve the aesthetics and to limit the graffiti painting, it was decided to plant ivy on the walls of the tunnel that have access to sunlight and rainfall.
- **Square at Rybaki Street** - Changing a city square that was regularly gridlocked with cars into an oasis of greenery. As part of the renovation of the square, decorative flowerbeds were created and stone bands of granite blocks were made. An interesting solution is the possibility of crossing the square among greenery on granite slabs. The newly established greenery consists of trees, shrubs and perennials. Apart from benches, baskets, bicycle stands or posts, a chess table was also mounted. Square at Rybaki Street is another element of the transformation of Poznan's street greenery, which will be an ongoing process for over 10 years.
- **Construction of a park in the location of Palacza - Księżycowa – Hevelius streets** that covers almost 4 hectares of undeveloped area surrounded by multi-family buildings.
- **The competition "Green Poznań"** is implemented as an initiative of the Mayor of Poznan since 1994. The competition is developed for Poznan residents, institutions, establishments and social organizations. Participants can submit their projects to the competition in five categories: balconies, home gardens, urban green spaces, plots within the Family Allotment Gardens and green belts.

Respondents of the survey were asked to assign the NbS exemplars to defined fields of actions (Fig. 3). Most activities are related to leisure and recreation, followed by urban green space and health and well-being issues.

Figure 3. Areas in which the NbS is implemented.

Despite the declarations of the respondents that they had heard about the nature-based solutions/green infrastructure it seems that the concept of NbS is understood differently and various activities that improve the quality of the city's environment and the quality of residents' life are perceived as NbS. Some of the respondents indicated that NbS activities and projects included: the construction of a rainwater collector that will contribute to improving the quality of Warta water, establishment of a traffic-calmed zone, aerators assembly on the system of connected Wilson Park ponds, installation of foggers and water curtains that are used during high temperatures in the summer and installation of new night lighting. Those surveyed also reported that activities and projects associated with raising the environmental awareness of residents were NbS. However, most of those surveyed were able to assign actions they undertook or projects which are planned according to the concept of NbS.

Photo: Stephan Kampelmann

Photo: Stephan Kampelmann

Source: Rotterdam Center for Resilient Delta Cities

Source: KuiperCompagnons.

2.2 Other opportunities for future NbS mentioned by the interviewees

- The **“Refill Project”** is an innovative and participatory solution to Poznan’s empty spaces. The project was mainly concerned with post-industrial real estate that could be converted to other purposes. This type of cooperation and participatory approach could probably be activated for NbS.
- A perceived opportunity is the creation of **new green areas in old, dense parts of Poznan**. The municipalities want to focus on pilot projects (pocket parks). The new rainwater strategy could be related to the developing of green spaces. The scope of the strategy is the entire city, but the most urgent interventions are located in the old city. There is some potential for using green spaces for rain water management in public spaces.
- **The open areas along the Warta River are another opportunity for future NbS development**. For example, by creating recreational areas, sports and active leisure zones. These areas could also provide a transport function (soft mobility, cycling paths). The area could also host a harbour for boats and ships (there will be a marina in the old town). New interventions in these areas would continue the work of projects related to the river, such as municipal beaches, revitalization of the Dom Kultury #1; smaller projects like three new playgrounds near kindergardens. They are also in line with the project of renaturalisation of the concrete embankments of the Warta river which the city supports.
- There is some **potential for green walls and green roofs for insulation**. The city has a lot of flat roofs (although no detailed review has been carried out); one interview saw higher potential for green roofs compared to green walls because of the latter’s higher costs in terms of energy and maintenance.
- **Innovative mobile greenery in Lazarz**. There is a lack of greenery in this high density area, which could be used as a testing ground for innovative mobile greenery.
- More generally, the **change of the political team after the last election** seems to have provided renewed energy for transition projects and a greater emphasis on a participatory approach in city development.

To recognize the possibility of including NbS in the work of those surveyed, respondents were asked about potential fields of inclusion (Fig. 4). All respondents declared willingness to cooperate in the field of NbS with other units. The smallest potential was identified in the field of creating a legal framework and raising finances or financing NbS.

Figure 4. The fields of possible inclusion of NbS in the work of the Department

3. Relevant documents

- Current research project commissioned to Arup Polska on water management strategy. The strategy document will be published in March 2018. The research has produced a map with 160 critical intervention points, 40 of which of key importance for the city. They are in a process of final diagnosis
- Study of Condition and Direction of Development adopted by resolution No. LXXII / 1137 / VI / 2014 of 23 September 2014. <http://www.mpu.pl/plany.php?s=6&p=294>
- Municipal Revitalisation Program for City of Poznań adopted by resolution No. LVI/1021/VII/2017 of 07 November 2017
- Spatial development concept of the Poznan Metropolis (KONCEPCJA KIERUNKÓW ROZWOJU PRZESTRZENNEGO METROPOLII POZNAŃ) 2016.
https://drive.google.com/file/d/oB8ZDvmog4d_VeUtzQThDeFQ1cVk/view
- GREEN SURGE (2015). Poznan, Poland. Case Study City Portrait. FP7 GREEN SURGE project. http://greensurge.eu/products/case-studies/Case_Study_Portrait_Poznan.pdf
- Documentation on the:
 - (from Greenery Department of Road Management Board)
 - Extensive documentation (including photographs) on realized projects by the Greenery Department of Road Management Board:
 - o Jezyce pocket park (from Greenery Department of Road Management Board)
 - o “A 100 trees for Lazarz”
 - Designs for 4 kilometers of embankments from the Water Management Board.
- Development Strategy River Water Poznan, Poland.
 - o <https://www.royalhaskoningdhv.com/en-gb/projects/development-strategy-river-water-in-poznan-poland/6025>
 - o <http://rdcrotterdam.com/projects/development-strategy-for-river-warta-in-poznan/>
- A study by the MPU (2012) including participatory methods on city development. The study showed the value of the green belt.
- The “Anty-bezradnik” guide on how the residents can participate in the development of the city (My Poznaniacy); greenery is not only recreation, but also improved living conditions, especially in dense and compact areas. Greenery provides for democratic spaces.
- The city currently prepares a “Urban climate change adaptation plan” (commissioned to the Environmental Institute of Wroclaw University).
- Future of allotments in Poznan <https://www.degruyter.com/view/j/quageo.2017.36.issue-1/quageo-2017-0009/quageo-2017-0009.xml>
- Poznan urban bee study <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13592-017-0554-y>
- Ancient forests and urban biodiversity in Poznan <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S161886671730078X>
- Conservation of vascular plant diversity in Poznan <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11252-016-0625-2>
- Floral biodiversity of allotment gardens <http://geokompleks.amu.edu.pl/data/floral.pdf>
- Assessing the synergies and trade-offs between ecosystem services provided by urban floodplains: The case of the Warta River Valley in Poznań, Poland <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0264837717307901>

Other resources of relevance to Poznan challenges

- Forestry commission - De-icing damage to trees [https://www.forestry.gov.uk/pdf/pathology_note11.pdf/\\$file/pathology_note11.pdf](https://www.forestry.gov.uk/pdf/pathology_note11.pdf/$file/pathology_note11.pdf)
- Space engagers Dublin <https://spaceengagers.org/>
- Re-using Dublin <https://www.reusingdublin.ie/>
- <http://www.turas-cities.org/pilot/12>

4. Finance

4.1. Experience in financing NbS

- The **Civic Budgets** instrument described above is a potential source of financing of NbS. It can therefore be seen as a co-creation mechanism to fund large and small-scale projects.
- A financial analysis is currently being carried out to understand whether it could be cheaper to direct rainwater from the city centre to the old bed of the Warta.
- The investment in the new rainwater management programme is likely to be financed by external sources of funding; two main EU funds (about water retention and biodiversity, respectively) could be used.
- According to some interviewees, the city budget allocated to greenery is not sufficient.
- Regarding the renaturalisation of the concrete embankments of the Warta river in the city center, the Water Management Board and the City of Poznan will apply for regional financing; regional tender was scheduled for December 2017. The Water Management Board is also in favor of applying for European funding, including the EIB. If there is a signature on the regional financing agreement by mid-2018, then by early 2020 the first stretch of the renaturalisation of the Warta embankment could be completed.
- It appears to be difficult to convince the financial department to make the investment in NbS due to missing numbers or narratives.
- In one example of a new housing development, the community participation has led to the design of a new greenspace with higher costs. Under this scenario the developer donated budget to the district which topped up the amount required.

According to the survey data, the financing of NbS is currently mainly from the City's budget (Fig. 5)

Figure 5. Sources of financing NbS exemplars.

5. Business

5.1. Environmental businesses that NbS could address

- There could be a role of real estate developers for nature-based rainwater management; but today's projects will be smaller compared to the historical projects, there will probably be smaller and medium retention centers ("miniparks"). The permits do not currently sufficiently specify water management issues.

- There has been regular cooperation between the greenery department of the Road Management Board and housing developers. There are regulations on developers to compensate for the loss of greenspace (for instance if a development requires cutting down trees).
- The development of the Warta as a waterway could provide business opportunities of different kinds. A number of places for future ports have been identified, these could be developed with the help of public-private partnerships.

5.2. Problems related to businesses

- According to some interviewees, the housing developers want to get as many buildings on the ground as possible, often removing trees and existing greenery. It seems to be particularly difficult to incite developers to create high-quality green spaces.
- There has not been a lot of cooperation between grassroots movements and housing developers in Poznan. The developers are seen to build on spaces that have not been used for a long time and often harbour rich biodiversity (e.g. the new and gigantic Shopping Mall Posnania).

6. Community

6.1. Identified environmental challenges that NbS could address

- Need for recreation areas in the vicinity of the city (“urban comfort zones”)
- Soft mobility.
- 'Greenspace' parking

6.2. City's experience in supporting the local communities through NbS

- The socialist period was presented by one interviewee as a very unfavourable climate for bottom-up initiatives, which more or less died out. On the other hand, people were faced with difficult situations, and they started to develop solutions individually instead of relying on collective interventions.
- Several interviewees noted that the inhabitants of Poznan are interested in nature; this can also be inferred from the orientation of many projects financed through the civic budget that were related to the environment. It seems that **inhabitants have increased their input on environmental issues** and city-making in general over the last years (since around 2010). The internet helped to consolidate grassroots movements and the social economy.
- One of the tools for engagement of citizens in city-making has been **the use of the civic budget tool** that is mainly targeted at small bottom-up projects.
- Poznan is changing quickly and there seems to be more potential today for social activity: “there has always been a lot of civic activities, but now it’s getting stronger”. There has been some involvement of citizens in city making, for example in the “**Kolektyw Kapielisko**”.

“My Poznaniacy” is a local NGO that developed views on city development. A number of local councilors are members of the organization. The existence of citizen-driven organisations is a value to the city that is often underestimated. Everybody is trying to get something out of the space. Moreover, next to the new park on the old Warta bed there is an civic initiative **“KontenerArt”**, which is mainly concerned with cultural or festive events but whose members also join in greenery activities. There is also a new exhibition space.

6.3. Challenges linked to communities in NbS projects

- The intensity with which communities have been engaged on environmental issues differs across the city. In the city center, Lazarz and Wilda, for example, there are a lot of people who want to get involved in projects and initiatives. On the other hand, there are districts like Piątkowo (in the North) which are more difficult to engage in participatory processes due to various reasons (lack of time, interest etc).
- Demand for parking/transport solutions.

7. Knowledge-infrastructure-environment

7.1. Environmental challenges identified that NbS could address

- Regarding innovative rainwater management, the first thing that needs to be changed is the awareness of the decision makers. For this purpose, Aquanet is using the example of Poznan’s traditional water management system and past realisations to show that NbS-type approaches were working in the past.
- In terms of rainwater management NBS can be more difficult to design, but do not require process control (nature itself regulates the flow of energy and matter). Operation of NBS requires effort /work, but technically is simpler than for example modernization of some advanced technical installation.
- The envisaged rainwater management system can potentially be designed to direct the rainwater away from the sewage. The strategy document by Arup Polska is expected by March 2018. The authorities (the city council of City of Poznań) can then adopt this document and develop a range of projects of different size (such as removal of certain pipes); the programme should be finished by the end of 2018.
- Urban heat island is becoming a greater issue with increase in impermeable surfaces and climate change impacts.

7.2. The city’s experience in dealing with technical challenges on the site related to NbS

- Problems of de-icing roads and impacts on trees.
- Years of urban tree planting and maintenance experience, including the new 100 tree planting initiative.
- Issues with delivering permeable paths, roads and public perceptions associated with dust from substrate-based systems.

8. Governance and decision making

8.1. Experience in dealing with policy and decision making for enacting NbS

- By and large, the policy of the city is perceived to be very much greenery oriented. However, several interviewees argued that more needs to be done to convince senior policymakers about the usefulness of NbS, or even to create awareness about NbS. There also seems to be a lack of more specific expertise on biodiversity related to urban green spaces.
- The City is using transversal “revitalization committee” and multidisciplinary “teams” including different departments of the City Council that helped to identify and develop areas in need of regeneration. There are a number of such “teams” in which coordination is happening. For instance, there is a team working on the revitalization of Sw. Marcin Avenue, which reports to the Deputy President of the City.
- The Deputy President of Poznan is personally in charge of greenery, and also in charge of the development agency, and the roads board. There are many different departments that are dealing with greenery in Poznan, enabling each of them to specialize. But, on the other hand, this means that decision-making is dispersed. How to coordinate all these important tasks related to questions such as the optimal number of parking spaces or introduction of new nature-based solutions is perceived as a challenge. Several interviewees stated this would call for additional regulations (ordinance) at the city level (or even at the national level) that would facilitate the work of the specialized agencies.
- There is an agreement and cooperation between the City of Poznan and the Water Management Board regarding the financing of the renaturalisation of the Warta embankment. Initially, the project was less about recreation. The City Hall developed the idea that the community would be directed to certain specific areas through the inclusion of stairways for access.
- It appears that participatory processes were strengthened after the elections in 2014. The new city government seems to give more voice to the citizens, for instance through the civic budgets (implemented at the level of the cabinet). The grassroots movements are increasingly becoming partners of the city in developing new visions and solutions.

8.2. Problems with governance/policy/regulation that impacted NbS

- Several interviewees noted that local spatial development plans can be incoherent with regional plans and strategies.
- There are some overlapping and compartmentalized competences and power regarding water management.
- Lack of one coordinator with cross-cutting knowledge from various city units dealing with the issue of water management.
- The selection process in public tenders tends to over-emphasize price criteria, which does not always lead to good results in terms of quality, performance and effectiveness.
- Cooperation between actors and stakeholders needs to be improved to meet common goals in a wider perspective.
- Higher levels of administration should be committed to innovative concepts such as green roofs, green walls.

9. Stakeholders

- **Biuro Koordynacji Projektów i Rewitalizacji Miasta (KPRM - the CN partner at city hall):** this department of the City of Poznan initiates and implements a number of city development projects. It is notably in charge of urban revitalisation and European projects, but the scope of activities is very broad (environmental, socio-economic, mobility, educational projects). The department reports to the First Deputy President of the City.
- **Aquanet:** a commercial organisation owned by the City of Poznan and 9 municipalities, serving ca 850000 inhabitants. 95% of inhabitants covered by Aquanet services; the other 5% is not (yet) connected to the grid.
- **Greenery department of the City's Road Management Board:** team of 10 people focusing on the green areas along the streets. This Board is an "urban entity" reporting directly to the authority of city administration; the people in the department on greenery on roads are mainly gardeners and landscape architects.
- **Water Management Board:** a governmental organization responsible for the basin of the Warta River. They work on the spatial development plans; they work on preventing flooding, water retention tanks. Aquanet takes water from the Warta River, and the sewage discharge goes into the river.
- **Municipal Greenery Management Board:** department of the city in charge of parks and green spaces, street greenery; the department designs, implements and maintains green spaces (maintenance is often subcontracted to external companies). Most of the parks in the city center underwent renovation over the last decade or so.
- **Local community councils (Rady osiedli);** has their own budgets (from the municipality).

Most of NbS are created in cooperation with other units of the City Hall (33%) or in collaboration with local communities (25%). Cooperation with NGOs or associations takes place in 10% of cases. The least popular is cooperation with volunteers and private investors.

Figure 6. Cooperation in implementing the NbS.

10. Driving themes for NbS in Poznan

- Maintaining and improving the system of green wedges and rings
- New small-scale green spaces in dense neighbourhoods
- Rainwater management
- Soft mobility and recreation

To recognize the potential of listed NbS to solve urban problems, respondents were asked their opinion on whether exemplars provided a contribution to climate change adaptation, health and wellbeing of residents, social cohesion and economic development and development of green jobs. The results suggest that NbS in the city focus mainly on social issues. Economic potential of NbS is still not yet discovered.

Figure 7. NbS exemplar impact according to selected Key Performance Indicators.

Nature-based Solutions and Connecting Nature in Poznan: where do we stand?

Conclusions from the CN workshop on January 16 2018.

To conclude this report, this section provides a summary of the discussions and ideas that emerged during a workshop on January 16 2018 that brought together CN partners, the interviewees that were met in November 2017, and some new local stakeholders from the City Council Board (Łukasz Mięka), a residential council in the Jezyce District (Michał Czepkiewicz), the NGO Fundacja Inspirator (Agnieszka Zdunek), the Municipal Urban Planning Office (Joanna Zomerska), the think tank Centrum Otwarte (Andżelika Jabłońska), the Department of Urban Planning and Architecture in the City Hall of Poznań (Katarzyna Podlewska), and Wielkopolska Investment Support Center Ltd. (Joanna Maciaszczyk).

During this workshop, the participants were provided with a summary of the exploratory research undertaken under WP3 under the lead of UEL by AMU and Osmos. The group also learned about a pocket park that was created in the “Gorczyzewskiego Skwer”; this allowed “zooming” into an interesting small-scale NbS project so as to provide a better understanding of how environmental projects unfold in the cultural, institutional, and social-political context of Poznań. The redesign process “Gorczyzewskiego Skwer” was presented by Maja Jaroszevska (from the Greenery Department of the Municipal Road Board) and Michał Czepkiewicz (from the Council of residents of the Jezyce District), who participated in all phases of the creation of this pocket park.

An important objective of the workshop was to create a common understanding about where Poznań stands at this point with respect to the NbS project(s) that will be developed in the framework of Connecting Nature. This section is an attempt to capture and summarize this common understanding. It could therefore facilitate the link between the exploration of previous experiences and available resources regarding NbS under WP3, on the one hand, and the planning of NbS interventions that will be conducted under WP2, on the other hand. In the specific context of Poznań, it is also an opportunity to ensure the commitment of higher levels of authority with the City Hall who will officially sign off the content of this document.

We use two relatively simple devices to summarize “where we stand” today with respect NbS in Poznań: the “Back to the Future” and the “Project-Environment Canvas” tools.¹

The “Back to the Future” tool has the purpose of organizing general attitudes and feelings in a group regarding key issues in the past and the future; it is a way to capture “the bigger picture” of attitudes toward NbS in Poznań without going into the details of individual projects or initiatives. The remarks that appeared to us as the most relevant and representative of the discussions during the workshop are shown in Table 2. Regarding a positive attitude towards the past (“**nostalgia**”), it seems clear that the historical configuration of the Poznanian urbanism is seen as a great achievement with enduring

¹ For more information on the methodology of these tools visit: <http://osmosnetwork.com/category/tools/>

positive effects on both the city’s population and the environment: although some Poznanians might not spontaneously refer to the system of green wedges and rings, they are likely to find certain specific spaces within the overall system as being relevant for their quality of life, such as the Malta lake, the extensive agricultural land or numerous allotment gardens. The “**hopes**” that were expressed for the future of NbS in Poznań are, at least at this stage, more diffuse: they concern specific ideas of interventions (such as pocket parks or post-industrial conversion projects), policy instruments (broader access to civic budgets), and more encompassing policy objectives at the regional or metropolitan scale (rainwater management; preservation of agricultural land). We also identified negative attitudes related to past events (“**trauma**”). They chiefly concern the environmental impact of the “race to development” that started in the decade after the end of Poland’s socialist period, reached its height in the early 2000s but is still ongoing today. This, however, is not the only negative experience that influences the attitudes towards NbS: others include the flood in 2010 and perceived problems in the way allotment gardens and civic budgets have functioned in the past. Some of these negative experiences have developed into “**fears**” for the future: Poznanians are concerned that the development might continue to “eat into” the city’s green infrastructure that they cherish. Another fear is that insufficient attention will be paid to instill sufficient awareness about the benefits of and need for sustainable urbanism among younger generations.

Table 2. Back to the Future: attitudes about the past and present of NbS in Poznań.

“Nostalgia”	“Hopes”
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The city’s system of green wedges and rings is a historic achievement that the people of Poznań are proud of. - The presence of traditional allotment gardens at scale (ca 90,000 individual plots in Poznań provide food and health benefits to many families) is also a strong asset that has been developed in the past. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More social gardens and pocket parks will be created around the city. - Post-industrial buildings will be transformed through attractive and mixed programmes (including housing as well as green/blue infrastructure). - Civic budgets for social and environmental initiatives will be widely available. - Rainwater problems will be solved (for instance through collection/use in new pocket parks). - The available agricultural land (ca 8,500 ha) will be preserved and put to better use for the city. - The city will solve the balance between the need for parking and greenspaces
“Trauma”	“Fears”
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Since the late 1990s, real-estate promoters have been engaged in a “race to development” that has reduced the system of green wedges and rings; a change in national legislation in 2003 has exacerbated this “traumatic experience” by creating a temporary regulatory vacuum. - A flood in 2010 created damage and showed the vulnerability of the city’s approach to rainwater management. - Allotment gardens are only in theory open to the public: in practice the gardeners have tended to fence their individual plots in to prevent intrusion from outsiders. - In the past it was hard for initiatives without institutional backing to access civic budgets. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong economic development of Poznań will continue to “eat into” the city’s green infrastructure. This fear manifests itself in different ways: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Allotment gardens along major roads might be lost or moved out of the city o Parking spaces create pressure on green space o Urban sprawl and associated mobility problems will decrease quality of life and reduce biologically active areas - Younger generations will not be sufficiently aware of sustainability issues

Gorczyzewskiego Skwer in Jezyce before and after the intervention that was studied during the workshop. Local residents represented by the Council of residents participated actively in the redesign.

The second summary tool we employed to capture the current state of reflection on NbS in Poznań was the “Project-Environment Canvas”. This tool was inspired by the “business canvas” methodology, which is widely used in the start-up community, but adapted to incorporate the more encompassing angle of integrated sustainability projects. In a nutshell, the “Project-Environment Canvas” helps to organize ideas and opinions in multi-stakeholder groups that work towards a common but still undefined project. It does so by collecting information on essential features of the specific actions that are envisaged (the “project”) without losing sight of the wider context in which the project will occur (the “environment”). The canvas provides a snapshot of the state of ideas at a given point in time; since all elements will inevitably evolve as things take shape, the canvas should be updated at regular intervals to keep track of the evolution of the project and its environment. The current version of the Project-Environment Canvas for the city of Poznan is shown on Table 3 below. Although the reflection regarding the project definition and specific actions to be taken is still at a relatively early stage, the Canvas nevertheless suggests a series of themes and suggestions that could be explored further in the next phase of Connecting Nature.

The **partners involved** are still mainly limited to the CN partners, although first outreach measures have been taken to work towards a cooperation with the Greenery Department of the Road Management Board and individual urban planning experts (notably Lukasz Mikula, who is not only part of the CN AMU team but also a member of the City Council Board and expressed interest to continue the collaboration). We think it will be key for the success of the CN project in Poznań to intensify the collaboration with other municipal agencies and urban planning experts like Mr Mikula as they represent valuable additions of competences and roles to the CN team. Moreover, we encourage the inclusion of private organizations – especially businesses and civil society organizations – as project partners so as to give them a voice in the project conception.

The **underlying values** that were expressed by the project partners still refer to relatively general principles. This being said, these values are sufficiently specific to identify key objectives that Connecting Nature and the NbS projects in Poznań should strive for. These values concern foremost the quality of life in the city, which appears to be a central driving theme of urban policies in Poznań, followed by a concern for equality and social inclusion of less affluent groups expressed in values such as “being a city for everyone” and the concern to provide young families with affordable housing in the centre. In line with the results of the “Back to the Future” exercise (see above), preserving and putting historical urban assets to a better use is another central value. The participants also expressed that they valued the social and cultural amenities of a thriving and dynamic city centre.

The **actions** that should or will be undertaken are perhaps the most direct expression of what a project is all about. In the case of the CN project in Poznań, the actions listed in Table 3 suggest that we are looking at a project involving a combination of scales and themes. Indeed, there is strong interest for intervening at the local level through small-scale interventions such as pocket parks or social gardens; but these small-scale interventions should be integrated into a broader development strategy at the scale of the entire city or even the metropolitan area, especially in light of their contribution to the preservation and improvement of the wider systems of green rings and wedges. We therefore suggest that future CN actions should be pursued at the local level through small-scale interventions, but that complementary actions should focus explicitly on how these local interventions relate to the preservation and improvement of green systems at the urban/metropolitan scale. This could require a clarification and/or synthesis of an integrated long-term development vision at the metropolitan scale, as a lack of such a vision could render small-scale interventions ineffective or even counterproductive. In addition to the reflection around the scale of physical interventions of the CN project in Poznań, other suggested actions are related to activities that could support the physical interventions. These concern for example the establishment of a constructive dialogue with real-estate developers and other representatives of the housing industry; at this point, the relationship between advocates of green space and real-estate businesses seems to be mainly conflictual in Poznań. Given the massive impact and power of real-estate development and a strong demand of Poznanians for

more and better quality housing, means that such a dialogue is indeed necessary to have a significant impact on how the city will evolve. There is even scope for win-win opportunities between NbS and real estate development, as the successful implementation of NbS could lead to increases in the market value of the building in its vicinity. Other supporting actions relate to the measurements of NbS benefits as well as educational activities that both could consolidate the impact of the envisaged small-scale interventions. An interesting hypothesis of how the link between local and metropolitan scales could be achieved is to focus on the theme of rainwater management. The City of Poznań is currently engaged in a reflection process on how to improve rainwater management to avoid floods such as the one that occurred in 2010. Small-scale interventions could include local rainwater management solutions such as water retention and infiltration that can be linked to this wider plan; educational activities and impact assessments could help to explain and monitor how small-scale rainwater management initiatives contribute to city-wide objectives.

If these actions were to be pursued successfully, **the output** of the CN project in Poznan could therefore include various small-scale NbS interventions around the city (including social gardens, pocket parks, municipal beaches or other forms of small green spaces); clear and intelligible links between small-scale interventions and integrated development plans at larger scales (e.g. regarding rainwater management); and a broad alliance for improving all aspects of quality of life including different stakeholders (overcoming the antagonism between conservationists and developers).

We now turn to the essential features of the broader environment in which the CN project needs to be embedded. The first of these features concerns **interest groups**, i.e. individuals or organizations that will be affected by the outcome of the project. Given that these groups have a stake in the project's success or failure we recommend that they should at least be consulted; if possible, some of them could become full-fledged partners of the project. At this point, broad categories of interest groups have been identified. In addition to the real-estate developers we already mentioned, these include residential communities and their representative bodies, and in particular the Councils of residents that appear to play a central role in urban projects at the local level that was underlined by the case study on the "Gorzyczewskiego Skwer" in the Jezyce District. Other important interest groups are large employers (such as universities and corporate groups) as these organizations are potential allies in a quest for a healthier and greener city due to their concern for retaining, attracting and motivating their employees. An interest group that has currently not been included in the discussion are private planning professionals; the latter are likely to become involved partners as soon as physical interventions need to be planned by architects, landscape architects, urbanists, etc. We therefore recommend to reach out to this interest group as soon as possible; a potential contact point for this purpose could be Piotr Kostka, a Poznań-based architect who also serves as the President of the Poznań-branch of the Polish Association of Architects. Finally, other municipal agencies that are not full-fledged partners should at least be considered as an interest group that will be affected by future NbS projects and whose cooperation conditions the projects' success.

The next item of the Canvas is concerned with **the needs of the thus identified interest groups**. Given that CN has yet to engage in a direct dialogue on NbS with these groups, the list of needs in Table 3 should be interpreted with caution and requires validation through the different participatory processes that are foreseen in the next stages of the project. Bearing this caveat in mind, it appears that among the central needs of the most relevant interest groups are solutions to the city's mobility problems (mainly a need of the residential population and their employers); more effective tools to limit urban sprawl and to protect green areas (arguably a need of conservationists and the residential population whose quality of life depends on access to green spaces); the need to reconcile densification, quality of life and the provision of more affordable housing in the city centre (a need of citizens eager to live in the city centre without sacrificing quality of life); better education on sustainability issues (a general need that was expressed by members of the municipality); the need to convince large employers and real estate developers of benefits from green and blue infrastructures at different scales (a "strategic need" of NbS advocates who need the buy-in from powerful actors in order to implement NbS in Poznań); and a less antagonistic relationship with real-estate developers and

clearer and more integrated long-term development vision at the metropolitan scale (which are also “strategic needs” of NbS advocates).

The resources that could be mobilized for the project depend very much on the specific actions that will be carried out. Since these actions still need to be fleshed out in more detail, only a few broad resource categories have been identified at this stage. These refer to the city’s vast agricultural land reserves (including the impressive number of allotment gardens) that could be useful for providing the physical space for NbS interventions. If these interventions focus on the theme of rainwater management (as we recommended above), the city’s new rainwater management strategy that is scheduled to be presented to the city council in March 2018 would also be a useful asset for providing a planning framework and a link to existing policy discussions in Poznan. Other resources of the city that could be useful for NbS implementation are post-industrial real estate (such as the former gas plant or the slaughterhouse) as well as the tool of civic budgets. As the actions undertaken by CN in Poznań will become more specific, more resources could certainly be added to this list.

Finally, **the overall outcomes** from which the larger community would benefit could include a more balanced development path that reconciles economic prosperity and environmental quality; green infrastructure providing measurable benefits to various social groups; a development model that preserves green belt and agricultural land around the city (i.e. containment of urban sprawl). If the above suggestions regarding a focus on coherence across scales and the theme of rainwater management are confirmed, potential outcomes could also include a stronger coherence between small-scale interventions and large-scale development vision (for instance in the form of a spatial NbS and connectivity strategy), more sustainable urban infrastructures and a compact city centre with less flood risk and better infrastructure for cyclists.

If one was to summarize the current iteration of Poznan’s Project-Environment in one sentence it could read as follows: “Integrating a diversity of small-scale nature-based solutions (such as pockets parks or social gardens) into dense neighborhoods will contribute to materialize a long-term vision of Poznań as a city of interconnected green spaces that reconcile high quality of life with sustainable infrastructures and the city’s rapid economic development.”

Table 3. Project-Environment Canvas for NbS in Poznań²

<p>Project</p>	<p>Involved partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CN teams from AMU and City of Poznań (KPRM) - Other CN partners - Greenery Department at the Road Management Board - Urban planning experts (e.g. Lukasz Mikula) 	<p>Values</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing high quality of life for all Poznanians - Being a "city for everyone" - Allowing young families to live in the city center - Preserving and improving historical assets: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o System of green wedges and rings o Allotment gardens o Agricultural land - Creating a thriving and dynamic city centre offering culture, leisure, shopping, etc - Provide better housing through NbS 	<p>Actions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plan and implement new social gardens, pocket parks and municipal beaches in dense areas lacking access to green space - Development of green wedge system within and beyond the city borders - Clarify/synthesize an integrated long-term development vision at the metropolitan scale - Engage real-estate developers, residential communities and NGOs in a constructive dialogue about the future of the city - Measure impact of small scale interventions regarding a range of potential benefits (quality of life, health, economic value of surrounding real estate, rainwater retention/infiltration, ecosystem quality, biodiversity, etc) - Develop educational activities on environmental benefits 	<p>Output</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Various small-scale NbS interventions around the city (including social gardens, pocket parks, municipal beaches or other forms of green space) - Clear and intelligible links between small-scale interventions and integrated development plans at larger scales (e.g. regarding rainwater management) - Broader alliance for improving all aspects of quality of life including different stakeholders (residential communities, large employers, real-estate developers, municipal agencies, etc)
<p>Environment</p>	<p>Interest groups</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real estate developers - Councils of residents - Young people in suburbs - Large private employers (e.g. Lech, VW, Glaxo, etc, etc) - Large public employers (City Hall and AMU) - Planning professionals (e.g. Piotr Kostka) 	<p>Needs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solutions to the city's mobility problems - More effective tools to limit urban sprawl and to protect green areas - Reconcile densification and quality of life in the city centre - Provide more affordable housing in the city centre - Better education on sustainability issues - Cost-effective solutions to flooding issues - Convince large employers of benefits from green and blue infrastructures at different scales - Less antagonistic relationship with real-estate developers (e.g. through win-win opportunities) - Clearer and more integrated long-term development vision at the metropolitan scale 	<p>Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Green belt with agricultural land reserves and allotment gardens - New rainwater management strategy (March 2018) - Post-industrial sites in city center, (e.g. gas plant, slaughterhouse) - Civic budgets 	<p>Outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A more balanced development path that reconciles economic prosperity and environmental quality - A compact/dense city centre with less mobility problems and less flood risk - Green infrastructure providing measurable benefits to various social groups - Development model that preserves green belt and agricultural land around the city (containment of urban sprawl) - Coherence between small-scale interventions and large-scale development vision - More sustainable urban infrastructures
<p><i>"Integrating a diversity of small-scale nature-based solutions (such as pockets parks or social gardens) into dense neighborhoods will contribute to materialize a long-term vision of Poznań as a city of interconnected green spaces that reconcile high quality of life with sustainable infrastructures and the city's rapid economic development."</i></p>				

² This canvas has been elaborated by participants of a WP3 feedback session on January 16 2018. It summarises the information from the interviews and discussions during the feedback session according to key dimensions of the "project" (in this case NBS in Poznań) and its "environment".

Appendix 1: Annotated city maps

Appendix 2: Examples of stakeholder map

Appendix 3. Questionnaire used for interviews

About the city

- Can you describe some of the major challenges / issues facing your city today? For example: jobs and employment, housing, skills availability, public space, air / environmental quality, climate change, noise pollution, social integration, mobility...

State of NbS

- Based on the following definition, where are NbS opportunities in your city?
*“Nature-based solutions are **living solutions inspired and supported by nature that simultaneously provide environmental, social and economic benefits and help build resilience...** through locally adapted, resource-efficient and systemic interventions”*
- Could you identify projects / plans /visions (built or in design phase) in relation to NbS in your city?
- Which do you consider to be other great examples of a success and which do you feel were very unsuccessful? Could you identify key aspects? This could be in terms of the quality of the communications process, the design, the construction period, unintended outcomes etc...

Relevant documents

- Could you list documents (planning, strategy, development...) you find most relevant to the topic in your city?
- Can you choose 5-6 relevant documents that you consider important for NbS within your city? Please explain why you think these are useful.

Specific questions

Only a selection of the following questions will be used during the interviews, based on the interviewee.

Finance (where relevant)

- How were city environmental challenges identified that NbS could address?
- How were NbS type projects determined to be implement? What benefits did you want to achieve?
- How was the scope of NbS defined?
- What was your city’s experience in financing NbS – what different sources of finance were used and how did they work out? How did you justify the investment?
- Did your city run into any problems with financing NbS at any stage?
- How did they overcome these challenges?
- What KPI’s and baselines were set?
- What would be your city’s lessons learnt/recommendations be for future financing?
- Looking at NbS from a cost -benefit perspective: explore your city’s perspective on potential financial benefits of NbS.
- What follow up studies were conducted?
- Were the results of the project those that had been hoped for? If not, why?
- How are the benefits of NbS being communicated?
- How scalable are the outcomes?

Business (where relevant)

- How were city environmental challenges identified that NbS could address?

- How were NbS type projects determined to be implement? What benefits did you want to achieve?
- How was the scope of NbS defined?
- What was your city's experience in supporting businesses through NbS – what businesses emerged?
- Did your city run into any problems with businesses at any stage?
- How did they overcome these challenges?
- What would be your city's lessons learnt/recommendations be for future supporting local businesses?
- Looking at NbS from a cost -benefit perspective: explore your city's perspective on potential business/opportunities benefits of NbS.
- What follow up studies were conducted?
- Were the results of the project those that had been hoped for? If not, why?
- How are the benefits of NbS being communicated?
- How scalable are the outcomes?

Community (where relevant)

- How were city environmental challenges identified that NbS could address?
- How were NbS type projects determined to be implement? What benefits did you want to achieve?
- How was the scope of NbS defined?
- What was your city's experience in supporting the local communities through the NbS – what community organisations or groups emerged?
- Did your city run into any problems with community groups at any stage?
- How did they overcome these challenges?
- What would be your city's lessons learnt/recommendations be for future supporting local communities and community groups?
- Looking at NbS from a cost -benefit perspective: explore your city's perspective on potential business / social enterprise opportunities/benefits of NbS.
- What follow up studies were conducted?
- Were the results of the project those that had been hoped for? If not, why?
- How are the benefits of NbS being communicated?
- How scalable are the outcomes?

Knowledge-infrastructure-environment (where relevant)

- How were city environmental challenges identified that NbS could address?
- How were NbS type projects determined to be implement? What benefits did you want to achieve?
- How was the scope of NbS defined?
- What was your city's experience in dealing with technical challenges on the site related to NbS – were there any particular novel solutions that emerged (particularly those for novel for your organisation)? How did you attempt to maximise co-benefits and minimise trade-offs?
- Did your city run into any problems with technical solutions?
- How did they overcome these challenges? Was the technical experience available inhouse?
- What would be your city's lessons learnt/recommendations be for future dealing with technical challenges?
- What KPI's and baselines were set?
- Looking at NbS from a cost-benefit perspective: explore your city's perspective on potential technical benefits of NbS.
- What follow up studies were conducted?
- Were the results of the project those that had been hoped for? If not, why?
- How are the benefits of NbS being communicated?
- How scalable are the outcomes?

Governance + decision making. (where relevant)

- What was your city's experience in dealing with policy and decision making for enacting NbS – were there any particular policy or governance outcomes that resulted?
- Did your city run into any problems with governance/policy/regulation that impacted NbS at any stage?
- How did they overcome these challenges?
- What is your opinion about governance, bureaucracy and institutional competences (and overlaps) in relation to NbS in your city?
- What would be your city's lessons learnt/recommendations for governance and policy?
- Looking at NbS from a cost-benefit perspective: please explain your city's perspective on potential governance/policy benefits of NbS.
- Is there a push for NbS in your city? Who is pushing it and why?
- Are planning conditions difficult or flexible NbS?
- Which are the effective policies and tools for driving NbS (IE laws and financing)?
- What internal structures supported the planning process?
- Were any governance structures set up to facilitate delivery?
 - What follow up studies were conducted?
 - Were the results of the project those that had been hoped for? If not, why?
 - How are the benefits of NbS being communicated?
 - How scalable are the outcomes?

Stakeholders

> Mapping exercise: Stakeholders (as necessary)

- What are the major actors related to NbS in your city?
- Is there any significant friction or relationships between certain actors? If so, between who?
- Which are the organisations you collaborate with?
 - How were various stakeholders included in delivery?
 - What main barriers did you experience with stakeholder engagement? How did you overcome these?

Driving themes for NbS

- Could you describe 3-5 action areas that could help further develop NbS in your city?